

Research Article

Smart Solar Sticky Insect Trap

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Abstract: *The growing demand for sustainability and reduced pesticide dependence has inspired the development of a smart solar-powered sticky insect trap that operates automatically using renewable energy and IoT monitoring. Reliance on chemical pesticides will cause serious environmental problems, pest resistance, and health risks. Therefore, this project introduces a smart solar-powered sticky insect trap that integrates IoT, solar energy, and a light sensor which operates without chemical pesticides. Findings showed that reduced usage of chemicals significantly reduces its effect on the environment and controls pest infestation through early detection and makes the integration with IoT possible; thus, farmers are no longer burdened by the rising costs of purchasing pesticides. On the other hand, this smart solar sticky insect trap is marketable for potential collaboration with an agrotech startup company or any smart farming solution providers for growers. This project also aligns with sustainable development goals such as responsible consumption (SDG12) to reduce usage of chemical inputs in the field.*

Keywords: sticky insect trap; solar-powered trap; smart agriculture.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Insect pests are a major factor limiting the productivity and quality of horticultural crops around the world. Their presence often causes substantial economic losses and threatens sustainable food production. To control these pests, many farmers still depend heavily on chemical pesticides, which can lead to pesticide resistance, environmental pollution, and the buildup of harmful residues (Damalas & Koutroubas, 2018). Prolonged and intensive pesticide use also puts farm workers and consumers at risk while disturbing soil and water quality and harming beneficial organisms.

Sticky insect traps are a well-known non-chemical option for monitoring and managing pest populations. However, traditional traps have several shortcomings—they require manual checking, are ineffective during night hours when many insects are active, and do not provide automated data recording. These limitations reduce both the accuracy and efficiency of pest monitoring.

To overcome these challenges, this project focuses on developing a smart solar-powered sticky insect trap that integrates renewable energy with IoT technology (Saranya et al., 2019). The device uses solar energy for continuous operation and includes automated light control and wireless pest data transmission. This enables real-time monitoring and supports more precise, eco-friendly pest management decisions.

The innovation aligns with several United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) – notably SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) through improved crop protection, SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) via solar energy use, SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) through reduced reliance on pesticides, and SDG 13 (Climate Action) by promoting sustainable, low-carbon farming systems (Tzounis et al., 2017).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 System Overview

The solar-powered sticky insect trap was made to be a self-operating pest monitoring device that uses both renewable energy and IoT technologies. The whole unit has four primary parts: a solar power and energy storage module, an adhesive trapping system with light control, an IoT-based data monitoring unit, and an outside protective container. The goal of the design was to provide reliable pest monitoring with minimal manual work while maintaining continuous operation under open-field conditions.

2.2 Power Supply and Energy Storage

A 12 V solar panel provided the main power source for the device. The panel was connected to a 12 V, 7 Ah rechargeable battery through a solar charge controller to ensure steady current flow and safe battery charging. This setup allowed the trap to operate efficiently during the night, with enough energy stored to run all sensors and lighting components after sunset. The battery capacity was selected based on estimated load requirements and average sunlight duration at the site.

2.3 Trap Assembly and Light Control

The trapping component was built around a yellow adhesive sheet mounted on a reflective frame. At the center of the unit, a warm light-emitting diode (LED) lamp was installed to attract insects, especially during nighttime. The LED was controlled automatically using a light-dependent resistor (LDR) sensor connected to a microcontroller. The light switched on automatically when ambient brightness dropped below a preset threshold, reducing unnecessary power consumption.

2.4 IoT Monitoring and Data Transmission

The IoT module used the microcontroller board as a central processor, integrated with a DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor, and a small counting sensor to register insect landings. Collected data were transmitted wirelessly, allowing remote monitoring through a mobile device or computer. Periodic calibration ensured consistent readings from both environmental and detection sensors.

2.5 Field Installation and Observation

Prototype traps were tested in an experimental horticultural area at a harumanis mango orchard, UiTM Perlis Branch. The units were positioned about 1.2 meters above ground level and spaced roughly 10 meters apart to prevent overlap in light attraction. Insects captured on the sticky

surface were identified manually to verify the automated counts. Environmental data, including temperature and humidity, were recorded simultaneously for cross-reference.

2.6 Performance Evaluation

The performance of the solar-powered trap was compared with a standard non-solar sticky trap. Evaluation criteria included energy reliability, number of insects captured, and overall usability. Improvements in capture rate and operational autonomy were noted as indicators of system efficiency.

Figure 1. Working prototype of the solar-powered intelligent sticky insect trap

3. FINDINGS

The prototype solar-powered sticky insect trap was tested under field conditions at a mango plot in UiTM Perlis, where the climate is typically hot and humid, with abundant solar radiation during testing period. The system operated continuously without power interruption. The solar panel maintained charging efficiency even during intermittent cloud cover, with the 12 V battery sustaining voltage between 11.7 V and 12.5 V during night cycles.

The automated LED lighting system switching on during night time and off after sunrise. A higher capture rate was primarily attributed to the LED light attraction during humid evening conditions, which coincide with peak activity of leafhoppers, whiteflies, and moth species common in Perlis.

Environmental parameters recorded by the DHT11 sensor corresponded well with field conditions. The online monitoring platform successfully displayed insect counts and microclimate readings in real time, confirming the trap's functionality for remote pest surveillance under tropical conditions.

4. DISCUSSION

The field evaluation in Perlis, Malaysia, demonstrated that integrating solar energy, automation, and IoT technology into pest monitoring systems can significantly enhance the efficiency and sustainability of insect management in tropical horticultural environments. The results showed

that the solar-powered sticky trap maintained stable operation under both sunny and overcast days, reflecting the suitability of Perlis' high solar irradiance for renewable energy applications in agriculture. Similar findings were reported by Cagorol and Sabusap (2024) and Telaumbanua et al. (2025), where solar-powered light traps performed efficiently under tropical field conditions, ensuring uninterrupted functionality and consistent pest capture performance.

The higher insect capture rate achieved by the solar-powered trap compared to conventional sticky traps highlights the effectiveness of LED-based illumination for nocturnal pest attraction. Under Perlis' humid and warm evening conditions, insect activity—particularly of moths, aphids, and whiteflies—increased after sunset, enhancing the performance of the LED-attracted sticky surface. This observation supports earlier findings by Saranya et al. (2019), who demonstrated that IoT-enabled pest traps using light-based attraction improved detection accuracy and capture rates in tropical climates. Likewise, Cagorol and Sabusap (2024) confirmed that solar-powered LED traps significantly enhanced pest monitoring efficiency in paddy ecosystems due to their ability to attract nocturnal insects effectively.

The IoT-based data transmission module in this system represents a significant advancement in automating pest surveillance. Real-time data sharing enables farmers to remotely assess pest population dynamics, minimizing the need for frequent field inspections and manual counting. This is consistent with the findings of Tzounis et al. (2017), who emphasized that IoT integration in agriculture enhances data-driven decision-making and operational efficiency. The use of environmental sensors, such as the DHT11, also allowed for correlation between pest activity and microclimatic conditions, demonstrating how temperature and humidity fluctuations influence insect behavior — a relationship critical for developing predictive pest management models (Saranya et al., 2019).

From a sustainability perspective, this innovation supports the transition toward low-carbon and data-driven agriculture, aligning with Malaysia's National Agrofood Policy (2021–2030). By reducing reliance on chemical pesticides, the system helps mitigate soil and water contamination while protecting beneficial organisms. Continuous overuse of synthetic pesticides has been linked to ecological imbalance, pest resistance, and health hazards to farm workers and consumers (Damalas & Koutroubas, 2018). The system's dependence on solar energy also contributes to energy self-sufficiency and reduced operational costs, echoing Telaumbanua et al. (2025), who reported similar economic and environmental benefits of solar-based pest control systems in rice cultivation.

Overall, the results confirm that the solar-powered intelligent sticky insect trap can operate reliably under Perlis' climatic conditions while improving pest capture efficiency and data accessibility. The innovation offers an environmentally friendly solution to pest surveillance and enhances decision-making accuracy in Integrated Pest Management (IPM) programs. These outcomes directly support SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 13 (Climate Action). Future research should focus on incorporating AI-based insect recognition, expanded communication networks (LoRa or GSM), and material optimization to improve durability and scalability across Malaysia's tropical horticultural production systems.

5. CONCLUSION

The solar-powered intelligent sticky insect trap proved effective under the hot and humid climate of Perlis, operating continuously through solar energy while capturing more insect pests than conventional traps. Its automated light control and IoT-based monitoring enable real-time pest data collection, reducing labor and improving pest management decisions. This sustainable system supports sustainable development goals by minimizing pesticide dependence and promoting clean technology in agriculture. With further refinement in sensor precision and connectivity, the innovation holds

strong potential for commercialization among smallholder horticultural farmers and smart agriculture initiatives in Malaysia.

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